

KINETICS OF THE REACTION BETWEEN POTASSIUM PERSULPHATE AND THE ALKYL IODIDES. PART II.

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The rate of the persulphate-alkyl iodide reaction increases with dilution and the calculated velocities are in good agreement with the observed values. The relative chemical reactivities of the alkyl iodides in the homologous series have been determined and the results are analysed on the basis of the equation $k = PZe^{-E/RT}$. P is found to be less than unity and there is a simultaneous decrease of activation energy and the probability factor in passing from methyl to *n*-butyl iodide. The secondary, tertiary and *iso*alkyl iodides are more reactive than the corresponding primary compounds.

Hecht, Conrad and Brückner (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1890, **5**, 289) found that the velocity of the methyl iodide-sodium ethoxide reaction varied with the dilution as $k_v = k_1 + \omega \log_{10} v$. Cox (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, **113**, 666; 1921, **119**, 143; 1922, **121**, 1904) observed this equation to be applicable to a similar series of reactions. Kappanna has indicated in the decarboxylation of trichloroacetic acid in water (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, **A**, **158**, 355) that the effect of dilution is no greater than with bimolecular reactions. These investigations are of value since at great dilutions the observed rates and those calculated from the Arrhenius equation are brought into closer agreement, as observed in a large number of reactions (Moelwyn-Hughes, "Kinetics of Reactions in Solutions", 1933, p. 79). Attempts had therefore to be made to determine the suitable dilution for comparable results.

Owing to the increasing importance of the alkyl halides in synthetic and preparative organic chemistry, various attempts have been made to study their chemical reactivities with a variety of reagents. Consequently, numerous papers on the subject have been published, (Brussov, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1900, **34**, 129; Menshutkin and Wassilieff, *ibid.*, 1890, **5**, 589, Wislicenus, *Annalen*, 1882, **212**, 244; Segaller, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **105**, 106; Burke and Donnan, *ibid.*, 1904, **85**, 555; Haywood, *ibid.*, 1922, **121**, 1904; Preston and Jones, *ibid.*, 1912, **101**, 1930; Slator, *ibid.*, 1904, **85**, 1286 and others). Most of these reactions are considered to be metathetical. Therefore, a study of the relative chemical reactivities of alkyl iodides with an oxidising agent like potassium persulphate would be of special interest. Further, this part of work was undertaken to determine the effect of

"weighting" the alkyl iodide molecule in this reaction with CH_2 groups, on the parameters of the Arrhenius equation $k = PZe^{-E/RT}$.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The analytical procedure has been described in a previous paper (Telang and Nadkarny, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 536).

Effect of Dilution.—0.2 *N*-Alcoholic solution (10 c.c.) of $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{I}$ and 0.2 *N*-solution (10 c.c.) of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ were mixed together and then made up to the required total volume with water. The reaction mixture was heated in the thermostat for two hours in each case at 50° . The effect of dilution was also studied with 50% alcohol (effective composition of the solvent) in place of water as the diluent. Table I contains both the sets of observations.

TABLE I.

Dilution (v) (litre/g.-mol.)	Velocity constant $k \times 10^6$ (with 50% alcohol).	Velocity constant (with water).	
		$k \times 10^6$ (obs.)	$k \times 10^6$ (calc.)
10	147.7	153.5	154.0
20	143.9	174.6	186.8
40	78.7	228.2	220.1
80	30.7	254.1	253.5
160	—	272.3	286.8

The Relative Chemical Reactivities of the Alkyl Iodides.—The alkyl iodides were prepared from their corresponding alcohols by the standard method, the alcoholic group being replaced by iodine in presence of red phosphorus. For the determination of the velocities of the different iodides, 0.2*N* alcoholic solution (10 c.c.) of alkyl iodide and 0.2*N* solution of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ (10 c.c.) were made up to 100 c.c. with water (dilution $v=50$) and heated for two hours at the required temperature. The results are shown in Table II.

The collision frequencies Z have been calculated from the equation (Moelwyn-Hughes, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 95)

$$Z = 3\pi N\eta\sigma_A / 2M_A \times (M_A + M_B) / M_B,$$

where M_B is the molecular weight of the solvent (water), M_A that of the alkyl iodide and other terms have their usual significance. As the effective

composition of the solvent is only 10% alcohol, M_s is taken as the mol. wt. of water. The Arrhenius energy of activation has been corrected for the viscosity factor, Rb in the relation $E = E_a + Rb$ (cf. Andrade, *Nature*, 1930, 125, 309). Within the range of 50° and 60° the temperature coefficients of the viscosity of alcohol and water are not very different so that the values of water are used for correcting the Arrhenius energy of activation. This effect in all cases is to increase E_a by 3.425 calories. So the theoretical velocities given below are corrected for this viscosity factor. As the Arrhenius equation is not accurately obeyed (*vide*, Telang, Thesis, Bombay University, 1939) the critical increments have been calculated from the values of the velocity constants at two temperatures only, *viz.* 50° and 60°.

TABLE II.

Alkyl iodide.	Relative chemical reactivity at 50° ($C_3H_7I = 100$).	Temp. coeff. k_{60}/k_{50} .	k_{50} (min. ⁻¹) (obs.)	k_{50} (min. ⁻¹) (calc.)	E_a (calories).	Collision frequency, Z (sec. ⁻¹).	$P = \frac{k_{\text{obs.}}}{k_{\text{calc.}}}$
Methyl	60	2.57	115×10^{-6}	444×10^{-3}	20,120	6.6×10^{13}	0.26×10^{-3}
Ethyl	100	2.51	192	989	19,650	7.0	0.20×10^{-3}
<i>n</i> -Propyl	54	2.09	104	456	15,760	7.5	0.23×10^{-6}
<i>n</i> -Butyl	8	2.00	15	$212 \times 10^{+1}$	14,800	7.7	0.20×10^{-7}
<i>iso</i> Propyl	356	2.87	683	906×10^{-6}	22,500	7.6	0.75
<i>tert</i> Butyl	68	4.27	130	244×10^{-10}	30,970	8.1	$0.53 \times 10^{+4}$

The relative chemical reactivities of *isobutyl*, *sec-butyl*, *n-amyl* and *isoamyl* are 151, 19, 13 and 35 respectively.

DISCUSSION.

The velocity of the persulphate-alkyl iodide reaction increases with dilution up to at least $v = 160$, and the velocity at a dilution $v = 160$ is about six times faster than (k_1) calculated for unit molar concentration. From a graphical representation of the dilution effect, it is evident that the most suitable dilution required for comparable results is $v = 50$, as this dilution is sufficiently great without causing much inconvenience regarding the bulk of the reaction mixture to be handled. Examining the values of the velocities with water as well as 50% alcohol it is obvious that the presence of alcohol retards the reaction rate

whereas water accelerates it. We do not yet attempt to explain the mechanism of the dilution effect.

Since the probability factor P , for the normal alkyl iodides is less than unity, the reaction is classed as a "slow" unimolecular reaction. A close examination of Table II reveals that the P factor decreases as the critical alkyl iodide increment E_A decreases. This concurrence shows that the slowness of the persulphate-alkyl iodide reaction is to be ascribed exclusively to the increase of the energy of activation necessary for the oxidation of the alkyl iodides by potassium persulphate. These results are analogous to those in some cases of quaternary salt formation (Winkler and Hinshelwood, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1147). The change from methyl to ethyl results in no alteration in P , but there is a marked fall in P from methyl to *n*-propyl iodide; further, the change from *n*-propyl to *n*-butyl produces a slight alteration in P . These observations are in fair agreement with the general hypothesis that in a series of straight-chain compounds, beyond the 3rd or 4th addition of CH_2 group, the effect on P is relatively unimportant. Yet, the variation in the Arrhenius activation energy is observed to decrease by about 5000 calories in passing from methyl to *n*-butyl iodide.

The order of relative chemical reactivities of alkyl iodides in this reaction runs almost parallel with that in the reaction with silver nitrate (Burke and Donnan, *loc. cit.*). Further, these data show the greater tendency of the cleavage of iodine from secondary compounds and still more from tertiary compounds; *iso*-compounds, however, are the most reactive. The differences between the primary and secondary compounds may be real or they may be due to a different mechanism being operative (*cf.* Conant, Kirner and Hussey, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 232; 1925, 47, 476, 488).

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